

ESTIMATION OF ELECTRIC CHARGE SIGNALS FOR PIEZOELECTRIC DAMAGE MONITORING OF GLASS FIBER EPOXY COMPOSITES BY FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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1 General Introduction

Polymeric composites have defects by the imperfect manufacturing or damage in service inevitably, and thus damage monitoring skills have been developed to improve the reliability of damaged composite structures [1-3].

One of damage monitoring methods for polymeric composites is the piezoelectric method introduced recently. The availability of the piezoelectric method was proved by researches about the piezoelectric properties and piezoelectric damage monitoring using Double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens of glass fiber epoxy composite materials [4-5].

In this paper, electric charge signals induced from polymeric composite materials were estimated by the finite element analysis and compared to the experimental results during Mode I fatigue tests of DCB specimens of glass fiber epoxy composite materials.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

DCB type specimens as shown in Fig. 1 were fabricated using unidirectional glass fiber epoxy preregs (UGN150, SK Chemicals, Korea) by hot-

Fig.1. DCB specimen configuration of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composites.

press molding method under standard cure cycle suggested by manufacturer, and then cut by diamond wheel cutter.

Overall length, width, thickness, and initial crack length were 150, 10, 4.0, 50mm, respectively. Electrode to measure or analyze electric charge signals were fabricated on the specimen surfaces of 60 mm apart from the loading position. Mechanical and piezoelectric properties of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composites with the fiber orientation of 0° are listed in Table 1.

2.2 Finite Element Analyses

Fig. 2 shows the finite element model for analyses of electric charge signals from composite DCB specimens. Finite element analyses were conducted using ABAQUS 6.5 using 20 nodes 3D piezoelectric elements (C3D20RE) under sinusoidal load of 15N with respect to the crack length.

Table 1. Mechanical and piezoelectric properties of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composites (USN150, SK Chemicals, Korea)

Mechanical properties	E_1 (GPa)	43.3
	E_2 (GPa)	14.7
	G_{12} (GPa)	4.4
	ν_{12}	0.3
Dielectric constant	ν_{23}	0.4
	ϵ_1 (F/m)	4.87×10^{-8}
	ϵ_2 (F/m)	4.47×10^{-8}
Piezoelectric strain constant	ϵ_3 (F/m)	4.54×10^{-8}
	e_{13} (C/m ²)	-0.106
	e_{23} (C/m ²)	-0.635
	e_{33} (C/m ²)	0.272
	Density (kg/m ³)	1980
	Fiber volume fraction	0.6

All the nodes on the crack surface were doubly defined to model the crack surface, and released with each other to represent the crack growth [3]. Nodes at the center line of the end surface were fixed and electric field of nodes on the lower electrode was set to 0 V/m. And then electric flux density of nodes on the upper electrode was analyzed.

2.3 Experiments

Mode I fatigue tests of composite DCB specimens were performed on the dynamic material testing machine (Instron 8526, Instron Co., USA) under sinusoidal load of 15N with 1Hz. Electrodes were fabricated using electrically conducting silver paste (SSP-102P, Seoul Chemical Industrial, Korea) for measuring electric charge signals of DCB specimens. Induced electric charge signals were measured by the charge conditioning amplifier (type 2626, Bruel&Kjar Co., Denmark) and the crack length were recorded by analyzing magnifier images every 1000 cycles.

3 Results and Discussions

Fig. 3 depicts the relationship between electric flux density and crack length by finite element analyses of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composite DCB specimens. Electric flux density began to increase when the crack length was about 60mm (front end of electrodes), increased sharply until the crack length was about 80mm (rear end of electrodes), and then decreased.

Since the piezoelectric damage monitoring of polymeric composite materials used the phenomenon of the electric charge output induced by the material deformation under the external load, the important parameter for affecting the electric charge outputs is the strain between electrodes.

Since there was no strain between electrodes until the crack tip reached the front end of electrodes, the electric charge signal was not induced. While the crack tip passed through composite specimens between electrodes, there were large strains and induce electric charges increased. After the crack tip passed, the strain between electrodes decreased very fast and kept small. Therefore, finite element analysis results also described this phenomenon.

Fig. 4 represents the measured electric flux density with respect to the fatigue cycle by Mode I fatigue tests of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composite DCB specimens. Electric flux density increased slowly after 50,000 cycles, increased abruptly after 85,000 cycles, and then scattered near the final fracture.

Fig. 5 shows the measured crack length with respect to the fatigue cycle by Mode I fatigue tests of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composite DCB specimens. After 46,000 cycles, the initial crack began to propagate very slowly. Crack propagation was visibly after 60,000 cycles, steeply after 85,000 cycles, and lead to final fracture.

Fig.3. Electric flux density with respect to crack length by finite element analyses experiments for piezoelectric damage monitoring of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composite DCB specimens.

Fig.2. Finite element model for analyzing electro-mechanical behavior of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composite DCB specimens.

In order to compare results of finite element analyses and experiments directly, measured electric flux density-fatigue cycle curve was re-plotted measured electric flux density-crack length curve from Fig. 4 and 5. As shown in Fig. 6, results of finite element analyses and experiments were similar trend except data near the final fracture.

Therefore, we can conclude that the finite element method can predict the electric charge signals of glass fiber epoxy composites for piezoelectric damage monitoring, and the crack length of polymer composite DCB specimens during Mode I fatigue tests by measuring the electric charge signals.

Fig.4. Measured electric flux density with respect to fatigue cycles during Mode I fatigue tests of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composite DCB specimen.

Fig.5. Measured crack length with respect to fatigue cycles during Mode I fatigue tests of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composite DCB specimens.

4 Conclusions

In this work, we analyzed the electric charge outputs of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composites with respect to the crack length by the finite element approach for piezoelectric damage monitoring. In order to verify finite element analysis results, Mode I fatigue tests also performed using DCB specimens, and the electric charge signal and crack length were measured. Experimental works were processed to electric flux density-crack length curve.

By comparison between finite element analysis and experimental results, estimated electric charge signals are well agreed with measured ones. Therefore, we can predict the electric charge signals with respect to the crack length by the finite element analysis for piezoelectric damage monitoring of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composites. Moreover the crack length can be estimated by measuring the electric charge signals during dynamic tests of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composites.

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Fig.6. Comparison of electric flux densities by finite element analyses and experiments for piezoelectric damage monitoring of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composite DCB specimens.

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